

Database for compilation of case data

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Achieving wider uptake of water-sm art solutions

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ABSTRACT

The deliverable D2.2: Database of measurement, risks for validating the technology usage according to quality needs has been prepared in T2.1.2.

This is a database to collect data from the participants in the different case studies. The database will be a knowledge base of the technology solutions, required quality standards for different types of resource reuse applications and user experience from each of the case studies. The data will aid validation of the symbiotic solutions and facilitate wider uptake.

This document is a revised version (version 04) of the original deliverable where information requested in the project review is included in Appendix 1.

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1 Introduction

For evaluation of the measurements and systematic monitoring of the case studies we have developed an online database system, which accepts measured data and presents them on the web. This system is a new trend of the industry on automation and data exchange in manufacturing technologies. It is also called fourth industrial revolution.

T2.12: Development of database for compilation of case data

A database has been developed to collect data from the participants in the different case studies. This database is a knowledge base of the technology solutions, required quality standards for different types of resource reuse applications and user experience from each of the case studies. The data aid validation of the symbiotic solutions and facilitate wider uptake.

The database is open access and publicly available. The input data are therefore restricted to data without confidentiality restrictions either by the utility e.g., due to safety reasons, or industries e.g., due to commercial/IPR considerations. A common data format has been developed for input and all project participants have access for input of data. There is the possibility to enter data from online measuring instruments and to enter offline data according to the possibility in the different cases.

2 Aim of database

The main purpose of the database is to collect measured data from the cases, visualise them and compare them with standards and laws and perform risk evaluations. This way we can proof health and quality risks in recycled technologies online or study the previous situations or failures. In the future database can be used for prediction of behaviour of the system or failures.

In the database we can use the online data sent directly to the database or offline data uploaded manually. Database system can evaluate the measurement data and pictures monitoring impacts in the field. From the time-lapse of videos from the field the growth of plants can be evaluated.

3 Database system

The database system is working automatically. Simply taking the data, storing them, processing them and create output for user according to (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Database process

3.1 Input to the database

Data from the measurements can be uploaded to the server automatically (directly from the monitoring equipment) or manually (from lab testing). Protocols supported by the server: FTP, SFTP, NFS, SMB, web access, other if needed (REST). The collecting server is at CTU a Synology brand server. The data are protected with system-level prevention (Create firewall rules, automatically block IP addresses with too many failed login attempts and enable Account Protection to reduce the threat of "brute-force" attacks from untrusted clients.). Data on the server is backed up to another server for safety reason every day.

Address of the database input: database.wider-uptake.eu

- Two types of login:
 - For reading:
 - Username: WUUser
 - Password: WiderUptakeDataUser
 - For data saving:
 - Username: WUData
 - Password: WiderUptakeDataSave

For each case there are separate folders to store data for better orientation.

AC-Accra	23.09.2021 10:24	File folder	
AM-Amsterdam	13.07.2020 12:25	File folder	
HA-Hamar	13.07.2020 12:24	File folder	
Metadata	10.11.2020 13:18	File folder	
PR-Prague	20.10.2021 10:20	File folder	
SI-Sicily	13.07.2020 12:24	File folder	
Standards	12.10.2021 22:06	File folder	
ST-Stavanger	29.09.2021 13:26	File folder	
Test	14.04.2021 8:57	File folder	
Logo.png	15.07.2020 13:40	PNG File	55 KB
WIDERUPTAKE Background.png	15.07.2020 13:43	PNG File	332 KB
WIDERUPTAKE Background2.png	15.07.2020 13:51	PNG File	292 KB

Figure 2: Folder system on the data collecting server

Data must be in standard format and the format cannot be changed due to sorting in the database. At the beginning, the format for the data has been set, but none of the users were able to follow the format. Thus, the format is now set individually for each case. Also, the online data transfer is a problem for most cases due to lack of knowledge with online data transfer.

3.1.1 Threshold and Standard Files

When evaluating measured values, we want to be able to relate these measured values to relevant thresholds. Thresholds can come from legal norms, from standards, or can be just set by researcher to setup boundaries of baselines for measured values. Researchers maintain the threshold values in Excel sheets, which are uploaded to the project dedicated storage (Standards). Data processing pipeline will process all these Excel sheets and make thresholds available in data lake for further processing and for visualization needs.

3.2 Database processes

Once the data are on the storage server the evaluation process can start. The database processes are based on MS Azure cloud technology. All data are transferred to the Wider-Uptake project running in the cloud. Work is based on tasks assigned to programmers. Each task is solved and evaluated separately. This way we can collaborate effectively even with the covid situation.

Figure 3: Tasks example of the database programming

Data are sorted then checked for consistency and errors. Now we have raw data ready for processes. The reason for this step is to have understandable and correct data. When evaluating measured values, we want to be able to relate these measured values to some thresholds. Thresholds can come from legal norms, from standards, or can be just set by researcher to setup boundaries of baselines for measured values. Researchers maintain the threshold values in Excel sheets, which are uploaded to the project dedicated storage (on FTP server). Data processing pipeline will process all these Excel sheets and make thresholds available in data lake for further processing and for visualization needs.

For output we use several programmed pipelines which prepare the data for visualisation.

Figure 4: Internal database processes

The internal database processes are hidden on the cloud, normal user cannot access it. Users can evaluate the results with predefined functions which are programmed according to the user needs and inputs. The possibilities of the evaluation and comparison data are very wide, and it is limited only according to available data and user imagination and skills.

3.3 Output of the database

Output of the database is available at <https://database.wider-uptake.eu/> as a normal web page. The login must be used due to the authentication for data protection. The web server is running on the same server where data are stored to keep the DNS name of the server for easy access. Prepared web page is stored on this server, data for the charts and pictures are uploaded based on widget settings and time range.

Figure 5: Login authentication via certification authority

The database is prepared in a two-level evaluation process. Beta version is on the address <https://database.wider-uptake.eu/beta/> and is used for preparation and debugging program code in the sandbox. The purpose of the sandbox environment is to experiment with technology, break and fix the issues and learn. The resource group called sandbox and within the resource group are following resources:

- Storage account - wideruptakesandbox01 with hierarchical support enabled (storage account with hierarchical support enabled are often called Azure Data Lake Storage Generation 2, or short ADLS G2)
- Data factory wideruptakesandbox01
- Functions app wideruptake-sandbox-python, is done in python primarily

Also, in the development account wider-uptake there is a project called sandbox with the repository called sandbox. In this repository are located all source codes for data factory and python functions.

When the code is ready, it is released from sandbox as the final version - deployment to live operation.

3.3.1 Web page of the database output

The web page of the database output is divided into the setting top bar and result windows.

Figure 6: Example of the database visualisation

On Figure 6 you can see the example of the database visualisation. There is several function buttons and display widgets for data evaluation:

1. Add widget button –you can add new window
 - a. Measured values –add a window for data series visualisation in time
 - b. Last webcam image –add a window showing last image from the site
 - c. Time-lapse over time range – display a window which is synchronized with data series for observing the plants growth dependent on the data
 - d. For future data evaluation more widgets will be added according to users' needs
2. Settings – users can use setting of the widget for quick visualisation. Some of the settings are predefined, or user can save his own layout for future quick access. Settings are transferable between users
3. Time scale settings for time-lapse pictures and chart synchronization
4. Time range setting for data

5. Login information
6. Example of time-lapse widget
 - a. Top bar – + button add the time-lapse picture
 - b. Top bar – X closes the widget
 - c. Bottom bar – shows the progress of the time. Button will run the time-lapse again
7. Chart widget – display values of the measurement in time. You can combine all measured values for understanding dependencies. Values can be also compared with different standards.
 - a. Top bar – + button add measured series
 - b. Top bar – data button provides data output in table with possibility to save it in Excel format for other evaluation
 - c. Top bar – X closes the widget

3.3.2 Database usage

Usage of the database output is simple – you can use the predefined layout settings or create your own to display the data. Synchronization the data series with pictures from cameras you can estimate the influence on the plants observed in the field. Advantage of customized output is quick access and visualisation measured data combined or compared together.

The database will be functioning during the project and developed for project users' needs. More measured data during the time will also increase the information value.

4 Conclusions

This document summarizes activities carried out in the achievement of T2.1 Development of database for compilation of case data. The database for storage and evaluation of the measured data was developed. It was developed based on MS Azure cloud technology due to wide range of functions and programming robustness. The database can be viewed on the web page, so it is possible to access it from internet web page browser anywhere. Measured data and pictures from cameras show the field behaviour to study the influence of different components of the recycled material (water, sludge) to the environment, on health, or other final product.

Now we are in phase of collecting data. For good analysis it is necessary to have long term data series to uncover information – such as hidden patterns, correlations – that can help with quality and risk analysis and predict behaviour of the system to make decisions before it will happen.

5 Appendix I

Development of the database system is continuing. New functions and data sets are being added according to user's needs. From users' meetings we are getting the response and needs which are implemented into the database output.

5.1 Data description

Description of the dataset is part of the data collection protocol. Delivery of the data description is the same as the data delivery and it is fully under the case studies responsibility.

Each dataset has some property such as:

- **Units of measurement** – for data compatibility comparison
- **Type of measurement** – continual (online) or occasional (offline)
- **Type of sensors or analysis** – for precision and sensitivity analysis
- **Comments** – other information about the measurement such as data over limit or errors from measurement. It is usually used in offline measurement

Some of the data description is already implemented – such as units and type of the measurement, some will be implemented when the case studies will add this information to the dataset.

The dataset description is/will be shown together with chart as additional information.

5.2 New planned features

From users' response we are adding these new features for better data evaluation and better user performance.

5.2.1 Database help

For better navigation and orientation in the user interface context help function will be added. In each window will be help button which will pop up on the side context help to explain widget or settings of the user interface.

5.2.2 Process visualisation

Now the database output provides only the dataset based on time series or combined with standards. According to user input the data will be sorted, analysed, and visualised according to the processes. The preparation of the visualisation is shown on next picture. From this visualisation you can follow the process for each parameter and identify the risk.

Figure 7: example of data visualised according to the processes

5.2.3 Description of the process

Each case study has their own scheme of the processes and measurement localisation in the process, which is important for better understanding of each measurement. When you click on the measurement point (red point) measured values will popup.

Figure 8: Example of process schemes with localisation of measurements

5.2.4 Deeper data analysis

In the future (when we will have enough data) deeper data analysis will be added such as:

- QMRA : Quantitative microbial risk assessment
- QCRA : Quantitative chemical risk assessment
- RCR : Risk Characterization Ratio
- PNEC : Predicted No-Effect Concentration
- And others

The development of the database will continue in the second reporting period in discussion with the partners in the different cases studies.